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Complexes of Copper(II) with 2-(*o*-Hydroxyphenyl) Benzimidazole and Related Ligands

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Manuscript received 27 June 1978, accepted 8 September 1978

A survey of literature reveals that studies on the complexes of 2-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl) imidazoline (HOPI_{mz}, Fig.A), 2-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)-benzimidazole (HOPBZ), benzoxazole (HOPBOX) and-benzothiazole (HOPBT), (Fig.B) have been restricted to their analytical applications¹⁻⁶ and effect of coordination on the infrared N-H and C=N vibrations^{6,7} of the ligands.

FIG-A

FIG-B

In continuation of our investigations on the structural aspects of substituted benzimidazole complexes⁸⁻¹⁰, we are reporting here the preparation and the results of spectral and magnetic measurements of copper(II) complexes with HOPI_{mz}, HOPBOX, HOPBZ and HOPBT.

It has been found that the neutral *bis* chelates of copper(II) of the general formula CuL₂ (where HL = HOPI_{mz}, HOPBZ, HOPBOX and HOPBT) are conveniently obtained by refluxing an aqueous methanolic solution of copper(II) acetate with stoichiometric proportion of ligand dissolved in methanol. The colour and physical properties of the complexes with these ligands differ remarkably from each other (Table-1), though all the ligands form six membered chelates with the same disposition of donor atoms (NO). In i.r. spectral studies the disappearance of (-OH) stretching vibrations of the ligands (HOPBZ at 2540, HOPI_{mz} at 2690, HOPBOX at 2280 and HOPBT at 2260 cm⁻¹) is doubtless due to bonding of the ligand through phenolic oxygen by deprotonation. The shift of (C=N) stretching vibrations to lower frequencies in the complexes indicate the bonding of the pyridine nitrogen to copper^{1a}. The complexes are insoluble in water but dissolve slight in DMF, dioxan and pyridine. As expected in DMF solutions, the complexes are non electrolytes.

The effective magnetic moment values of *bis* 2-(*o*-phenolato)-imidazoline copper(II) and *bis* 2-(*o*-phenolato) benzimidazole copper (II) fall in the range of planar or distorted octahedral copper(II) complexes; while those of *bis* 2-(*o*-phenolato) benzoxazole copper(II) and *bis* 2-(*o*-phenolato) benzothiazole copper(II) are similar to common octahedral or tetrahedral copper(II),^{11,12} (Table-1).

The mull electronic absorption spectra of complexes exhibit two or three very intense bands above 25,000 cm⁻¹ (Table-2), probably arising from n-π*, π-π* and charge transfer transitions. It is observed that solid reflectance or mull spectra of some complexes differ appreciably from the solution spectra in dioxan, DMF or pyridine. The energies of bands indicate that these complexes have different structures in solid and solution phases.

The reflectance bands of [Cu(OPImz)₂] located at 17860, 21740(sh) and 23260 cm⁻¹ have higher energies than the octahedral or tetrahedral copper(II) complexes, but fall in the range of planar copper(II) complexes^{13,14}. In DMF, dioxan, or pyridine solutions the d-d band shifts to lower energy and only one broad and medium absorption band is observed

TABLE-1 ANALYTICAL RESULTS, COLOUR AND MAGNETIC MOMENT VALUES (AT 308.5°A) OF COPPER(II) COMPLEXES

Complex	Colour	% of Cu	% of N	μ_{eff} in B.M.
[Cu(OPImz) ₂]	Dull-Gray	Found : 16.34	14.41	1.89
		Reqd. : 16.46	14.52	
[Cu(OPBZ) ₂]	Brick-Red	Found : 13.01	11.56	1.77
		Reqd. : 13.18	11.62	
[Cu(OPBOX) ₂]	Cream colour	Found : 13.31	5.84	2.07
		Reqd. : 13.13	5.79	
[Cu(OPBT) ₂]	Yellowish-Brown	Found : 12.10	5.31	2.04
		Reqd. : 12.31	5.43	

NOTES

TABLE—2 SPECTRAL BAND POSITIONS OF COPPER(II) COMPLEXES WITH THEIR PROBABLE ASSIGNMENTS.

Complex	Medium	Band positions cm ⁻¹	Assignment of bands	Complex	Medium	Band positions cm ⁻¹	Assignment of bands
[Cu(OPImz) ₂]	Solid	25,000 sh	C-T	[Cu(OPBZ) ₂]	Solid	27,780 sh	C-T
		23,260 m	² B _{1g} → ² A _{1g}			21,280 m	² B _{1g} → ² B _{2g}
		21,740 sh				12,999 w.br	
	DMF	17,860 m	² B _{1g} → ² B _{1g}		Nujol mull	31,250 s	π→π*
		28,570 vs	C-T			27,400 sh	C-T
	16,950 m	E _g →T _{2g}	21,280 m			² B _{1g} → ² B _{2g}	
Dioxan	28,570 vs	16,670 m	C-T E _g →T _{2g}	DMF	13 330 w	C-T	
					31,450 s		
Pyridine	29,850 vs	16,670 m	C-T E _g →T _{2g}	29,850 s	C-T		
				27,780 s			
[Cu(OPBOX) ₂]	Solid	26,310 s	C-T	[Cu(OPBT) ₂]	Solid	24,390 s	C-T
		14 920 w. br	E _g →T _{2g}			13,700 m. br	E _g →T _{2g}
	DMF	34 480 s	n→π*		DMF	29,850 s	π→π*
		31,060 s	π→π*			26,320 sh	C-T
		29,650 s	C-T			21,740 sh	² B _{1g} → ² B _{2g}
		27,030 s					
		21,280 m	² B _{1g} → ² B _{2g}				
		19,610 m	² B _{1g} → ² A _{1g}				

in the region 16950-16790 cm⁻¹. The energy of the band falls in the range of octahedral copper(II) complexes^{18,19}. Thus, the absorption spectra of [Cu(OPImz)₂] clearly indicate that octahedral copper(II) ions exist in solutions due to axial interaction of solvent molecules.

The solid reflectance or mull absorption band of [Cu(OPBZ)₂] located at 21280 cm⁻¹ can be assigned to ²B_{1g}→²B_{1g} transition in planar geometry. The very weak band observed at 12990 cm⁻¹ is attributed to some tetragonal distortion of the planar structure. The DMF or dioxan solution of [Cu(OPBZ)₂], like the solid state spectrum, also exhibits only one d-d band at 21280 cm⁻¹. Therefore the complex has similar structure both in solid and solution phase.

The crystal structure determination of [Cu(OPBOX)₂] has shown that it is built up of parallel and almost planar [Cu(OPBOX)₂] molecules, in which the copper(II) atoms are linked together by weak Cu-O bond along the b-axis and the coordination about Cu(II) is distorted octahedral¹⁷. The weak and broad band observed in the reflectance spectrum of [Cu(OPBOX)₂] at 14920 cm⁻¹ is assigned to E_g→T_{2g} transition in distorted octahedral ligand field. In DMF solution the polymer is broken up and probably some planar species of [Cu(OPBOX)₂] exist which exhibit medium band at 19610 and 21280 cm⁻¹ attributed to ²B_{1g}→²B_{2g} and ²B_{1g}→²A_{1g} transition respectively. The medium and broad reflectance band of [Cu(OPBT)₂] observed at 13700 cm⁻¹ is assigned to E_g→T_{2g} transition in distorted octahedral field. In DMF solution the band at 13700 cm⁻¹ disappears and a new weak band is observed at 21740 cm⁻¹. This new band is assigned to ²B_{1g}→²B_{2g} transition in the planar [Cu(OPBT)₂] species formed by the cleavage of associated octahedral [Cu(OPBT)₂] molecules in solution.

From spectral results it is suggested that all copper(II) complexes have almost planar arrangement of [Cu(NO₂)₂] group, but due to axial interaction of ring oxygen or sulphur atom, octahedral environment is achieved around copper(II) atom in case of [Cu(OPBOX)₂] and [Cu(OPBT)₂]. In solid state the axial interaction of free N-H nitrogen atom does not appear to exist in [Cu(OPImz)₂] and [Cu(OPBZ)₂] molecules. Therefore the solid [Cu(OPImz)₂] and [Cu(OPBZ)₂] are almost planar. These spectral conclusions have also been supported from the magnetic moment values of the complexes. From the spectra of complexes in solutions, it is concluded that axial interaction of solvent molecules around planar copper(II) complexes [Cu(NO₂)₂] is negligible with bulky ligand molecules, but it predominates in case of smaller ligand molecules like HOPImz.

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Studies on the Catalytic Hydration of Cyano-Compounds to Amides

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Manuscript received 4 October 1978, revised 15 February
1979, accepted 22 February 1979

The amides are generally prepared by the hydration of cyano-compounds. This reaction is catalysed by acids or alkalis in homogeneous phase. This has been reported by several investigators^{1,2}.

The disadvantage inherent in the use of alkalis or mineral acids are the formation of the corresponding carboxylic acids as by products. This results in corresponding decrease in the yield of the amides. Further, the product of such reaction would consist of a solution of a mixture of amides, the acid and the catalyst used which necessitates a rather elaborate separation step.

It should be possible to avoid or to minimise the hydrolytic action by the use of water insoluble cata-

lyst of either acidic or basic nature. With this concept, various metallic oxides like V_2O_5 , MnO_2 , Cr_2O_3 , etc. were tested and were tested and were found to be useful in this connection.

The general procedure for hydration is accomplished by refluxing an aqueous solution of the cyano-compound for 3 to 10 hours in water with a suitable amount of catalyst. After the reaction, the catalyst is filtered off. The catalyst can be reused after proper drying in an air-oven. The filtrate is processed for the separation of cyano-compound and the amide generally by the extraction with ether. The aqueous extract after evaporation yields a solid mass which consists of the crude amide. Similarly, the unreacted cyano-compound is obtained by the evaporation of the ethereal extract. The identity of the amide as well as the cyano-compound is confirmed by I.R. spectroscopy.

Results and Discussions

From Table-1, it is observed that of all the catalysts, manganese dioxide exhibited highest selectivity towards hydration of pyridine carbonitrile to pyridine carboxamide. Therefore exhaustive investigation on different aspects of hydration reaction has been carried out with this catalyst to optimise the yield of pyridine 3-carboxamide and pyridine 4-carboxamide.

Since, the method of the preparation of the catalyst modifies the surface properties which in turn governs the catalytic activity, different methods of preparation of manganese dioxide were adopted and their activities were tested.

From Table 2, it was found that manganese dioxide, prepared by the reduction of $KMnO_4$ with manganous salts, exhibits special properties and characteristics on the catalyst resulting in the highest selectivity of the catalyst.

TABLE-1. COMPARATIVE EFFICIENCY OF DIFFERENT CATALYSTS IN THE HYDRATION OF PYRIDINE CARBONITRILE TO PYRIDINE CARBOXAMIDE

Catalyst	Wt. of cyano-compd. gms.	Solvent cc	Reaction time hr.	Temp. °C	Yield of Amide gms.	Cyano-compd recovered gms.
V_2O_5 (1 gm)	4. C.P. 10 gms.	Water 35 cc	5	100°	1 gm.	6.3 gm.
MnO_2 (1 gm)	3. C.P. 5 gms.	Water 35 cc	5	100	5.37 gm	-
Cr_2O_3 (1 gm)	3. C.P. 4 gms.	Water 35 cc	5	100	1.3 gm	0.9 gm.

TABLE-2. COMPARATIVE EFFICIENCY OF MnO_2 CATALYST PREPARED BY DIFFERENT METHODS
1 gm. of MnO_2 and 5 gms. of pyridine 3-carbonitrile in each case

Catalyst	Wt. of Pyridine 3-carbonitrile gms.	Water cc.	Residence time hr.	Temp. °C	Yield of Amide gm.	Nitrile recovered gm.
A	5	35	5	100	5.5	Nil
B	5	35	5	100	1.75	1.08
C	5	35	5	100	0.32	2.07
D	5	35	5	100	5.37	nil
E	5	35	5	100	5.7	nil

A- MnO_2 from Mn-acetate + H_2SO_4 + $K_2S_2O_8$

B- MnO_2 from $MnCl_2$, $4H_2O$ + $KMnO_4$.

C- MnO_2 from $Mn(NO_3)_2$ + H_2O heated upto 400°

D- MnO_2 from $KMnO_4$ + $MnCl_2$, $4H_2O$, heated upto 500°. for 3 hours.

E- MnO_2 from $MnSO_4$ + $KMnO_4$.

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